

The Influence of Peer Social Support on Adolescent Adjustment in Islamic Boarding School

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Abstract— This study is aimed to find out the influence of peer social support on the adolescent adjustment in Islamic Boarding School. Samples were selected by using probability sampling technique with total 278 adolescents in Darularafah Raya Islamic boarding school. Data was collected by using adjustment scale and peer social support scale. The data analyzed statistically by using simple regression. The result of this study showed that there is a significant influence between peer social support and adolescent adjustment Islamic boarding school.

Keywords— Adolescents, peer social support, adjustment, islamic boarding school.

I. INTRODUCTION

Islamic boarding school is one of alternative educational institution for parents to increase their children's quality of faith, piety to God, discipline, hard work, intelligence, and skill. According to Bawarni (1993), Islamic boarding school as a quarters and educational institution with religious atmosphere is a place where the students are called "santri" and the teachers are called "ustadz".

Generally, "santri" are adolescents when they first start studying in Islamic boarding school with a range age between 12-13 to 18-19 years old (Rachman, 2010; Pritaningrum & Hendriani, 2013). This is with accordance to the statement of Monks, Knoers, and Hadito (2002) that adolescents are in age of 12-15 years old (early teenager), 15-18 (mid-teenager), and 18-21 (late teenager).

In this period, they are faced with many transition situations. According to Hurlock (1997), transition from childhood to adolescence could trigger high emotional tension due to physical and hormonal changes. Therefore, this period is known as a time of storm and stress. Elias, Tobias, and Friedlander (1999) also stated that there are many changes felt by children when they move from elementary school to junior high school where the building might be bigger than in elementary school, there are more teachers, friends, and certainly

subjects of study. Moreover, Islamic boarding school has special religious related curriculum such as Arabic, Tafsir (interpretation of Qur'an), Qur'an and Hadist, Aqidah (Creed) Akhlaq (Islamic morality), Islamic culture history, Fiqh (laws in Islam), and others (Pritaningrum & Hendriani, 2013). Based on those facts mentioned before, adolescents will face difficulties and need time to adjust with every regulation, curriculum, activity and habit in Islamic boarding school.

Adjustment is a mental and behavioral response so that individuals can succeed in overcoming their internal needs, tension, frustration, and conflicts originating from within the

individual well (Schneider, 1964). Adolescents who are able to balance their self and environment demands by the way that can be accepted by their environment means that they have good adjustment. According to Schneider (1964), good adjustment is a reaction showed by every person to their self and environment efficiently, usefully, wisely, and satisfyingly despite the limitation and personality style they have. On the other hand, if the reactions showed are not satisfying and efficient, it could be said that the adjustment ability is not good (Desmita, 2009). They with bad adjustment to their environment could generate various negative things such as irresponsible behavior, unsafe feeling, aggressiveness, and could force them to get home sooner when they are in a new or foreign environment and give up easily to a problem. They will also become too imaginary to overcome dissatisfaction and using coping mechanism such as projection, rationalization and displacement (Hurlock, 1997).

Social support is one of the factors that effects adolescents. Adolescents with good social support from their environment will cope with various problems and their transition period well (Cutrona, 1996). According to Sarafino (2006), social support can inhibit negative effects caused by various tension so that it helps individual cope with pressing situation. Moreover, adolescents live in Pesantren are far away from their parents that the support obtained so far in home has. Van Tiburg and Vingerhoets (2005) explained that someone who is separated from his house will directly or indirectly lose the support he usually receives in his environment such as family or the other social environments.

In adolescence, friends become emotional support that is preferred to replace parents. Hurlock (1980) stated that peer influence attitudes, conversations, interests, appearance, and behavior more than families. When living in Islamic boarding school, teens interact more with peers in both the dormitory and in the classroom. Peers can be a reference, listener, role model, companion, critic diminished and advisor (Richey & Richey, 1980; Tokuno, 1986). The good social support from environment can help someone to overcome problems and also face the transition period appropriately (Cutrona, 1996). On the other hand, lack or absence of social support obtained from environment can make individuals feel alienated and worthless (Pearson, 1978).

In connection with the explanation above, there is the influence of peer social support on adjustment. Therefore, this study aims to look at the effect of peer social support on adolescence adjustment in Islamic boarding school.

II. OBJECTIVES & METHODS

The purpose of this study was to determine the influence of peer social support on adolescent adjustment in Islamic boarding school. This study used probability sampling technique which provided equal opportunities for all population subjects chosen as research samples (Sugiyono, 2014). The study involved 278 adolescents in Darularafah Raya Islamic boarding school. The data of research was collected by using the adjustment and social support scale.

The adjustment scale is arranged based on characteristics of adjustment according to Schneider (1964). This scale uses a Likert scale model with 5 alternative answer choices. Scale consists of a favorite statement that is worth 5 (very appropriate), 4 (appropriate), 3 (neutral), 2 (inappropriate), up to 1 (very inappropriate) and unfavorable which is worth 1 (not suitable), 2 (appropriate), 3 (neutral), 4 (inappropriate), up to 5 (very inappropriate). Adjustment scale has 38 items with a reliability value of 0.948.

The scale of peer social support is based on the types of social support based on the theory of Sarafino (2002). This scale uses a Likert scale model with 5 alternative answer choices. The scale consists of favorite statements that are worth 5 (very appropriate), 4 (appropriate), 3 (neutral), 2 (inappropriate), up to 1 (very inappropriate) and unfavorable which is worth 1 (not appropriate), 2 (appropriate), 3 (neutral), 4 (not suitable), up to 5 (very not corresponding). Peer social support has 37 items with a value of reliability of 0.960.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The data analysis method used in this study is a simple regression method where data is processed with the SPSS for windows version 16 program. The test of assumptions was made before analyzing the data includes the normality test and linearity test. Both are fulfilled so that data analysis with simple regression can be done. As for the results is as follows:

TABLE 1. The result of hypothesis test

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F	Sig.
1	.444 ^a	.197	.194	67.783	.000 ^a

Table above showed that there is a significant influence of peer social support on self-adjustment (F count = 67,783, p<0.05). Besides, the value of the determinant coefficient (R2) is 0.197, which means that peer social support influences adjustment by 18.6%, while the rest 80.6% are caused by other factors that not examined in this study.

TABLE 2. The results of a simple regression equation of peer support influence on adjustment

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	96.669	5.823		16.600	.000
	Peer social supports	.345	.042	.444	8.233	.000

Regression equation analysis showed that the direction of influence from emotional intelligence towards aggressive behavior is positive where the higher the peer social support obtained, the higher the ability of adjustment.

The result of this research hypothesis which states that there is an influence of peer social support on adolescent adjustment is in line with the result of study of Karneva and Hermaleni (2018) which stated that there was a significant influence between social support on student’s adjustment in boarding school. As well the finding of Mahmudi and Suroso (2014) in their research that individuals who obtain social support can adjust to their environment easily, because they never feel alone when having to face all the problems. Various supports obtained from the environment can change an individual's perception of a negative events and reduce the potential for the emergence of new stress or prolonged stress (Sarafino, 2004). In other words, social support will facilitate individuals to overcome problems in their daily lives so that they are able to adjust to his environment.

Peers play significant role in adolescent’s life. Peer group could be one of supports sources that provides a safe place to express their opinion, admit their weakness, and look for help to solve problems (Santrock, 2007). Peer environment is also important for adolescents because the strength of peer’s influence will reach its peak in early adolescence. That environment is a place where adolescents doing their activities together with the norms that were determined by that peer group itself (Mappiare, 1982; Papalia, Olds, & Feldman, 2011).

IV. CONCLUSION

It can be concluded based on the result of this study that peer social support gives positive influence on adolescent adjustment in Islamic boarding school with effective contribution of 19,4%. It means that the higher the social support obtained by adolescent from his peers, the higher the ability of his adjustment. Conversely, the lower the social support obtained by adolescent from his peers, the lower the ability of his adjustment.

The results of this study could be guidance for further investigations on adjustment and intervention of peer social support, especially for Islamic boarding school.

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